

SURFACE MMCS ON A TI-6AL-4V ALLOY PRODUCED BY COMBINING LASER NITRIDING AND POWDER ALLOYING

C. Hu, H. Xin and T.N. Baker

*Metallurgy and Engineering Materials Group, Department of Mechanical Engineering
University of Strathclyde, Glasgow G1, UK*

SUMMARY: Laser processing, which normally involves gaseous alloying by combining laser melting with nitriding, has been developed to produce better surface properties. Surfaces having hardness >2000 (HV0.1) have been produced, but rarely in a crack-free alloy and then only with sheet < 7 mm thickness. The present work describes a combined alloying approach as an alternative to gaseous laser nitriding, with the aim of overcoming the cracking problem while providing better tribological properties than the untreated material. Several types of powder were preplaced on the surface prior to the laser nitriding. Abrasive wear testing was conducted to determine the improvement in the surface wear resistance after the nitriding plus powder alloying process. The microstructures developed in the laser processing were examined and the cracking tendencies studied for all the processed surfaces.

KEYWORDS: laser processing, Ti-6Al-4V alloy, hardness, wear resistance, nitriding, powder alloying, melt pool

INTRODUCTION

The application of titanium alloys which require good wear or erosion resistance has been restricted, despite their attractive strength to weight ratio, due to their poor tribological properties. Therefore, laser nitriding of titanium alloys has been extensively investigated with the aim of improving the surface properties [1-5]. The hardness was reported to reach 1800HV, when a commercial purity titanium alloy was treated by a CO₂ laser with a Gaussian energy distribution under a pure nitrogen environment [4]. The wear resistance significantly increased [2]. However, cracking on the nitrided surface was recognised as a critical problem in laser nitriding of titanium alloys [1-7]. The tendency to cracking has been found to relate to the processing conditions, the nitrogen concentration in the environment and the thickness of the specimen. Although the residual stress could be reduced and cracking eliminated when a dilute nitrogen environment was used for the processing [2-4, 6-7], the dilution of the nitrogen concentration equates to less effective tribological properties. For example, the surface laser nitriding of Ti-6Al-4V (Ti64) alloy using 100v%N gave a surface hardness greater than 850 HV, while that using 40v% had a value of ~650 HV [5].

Obviously, the titanium nitride formed during the process, on one hand, is the major phase to enhance the material surface properties, and on the other hand, is a cause of cracking as well as the rapid cooling rate in laser processing. The quantity of the titanium nitride formed in the melt

has a significant influence on the tendency to cracking. The purpose of the present work is to explore a new technique of combining laser nitriding and powder alloying to compensate the reduction of the surface properties due to the decrease in the amount of titanium nitrides in the melt when the quantity of the titanium nitride is controlled below a critical level to avoid cracking.

Four types of powders, or mixtures of powders, were chosen. These powders were preplaced on the surface prior to the laser scanning under a nitrogen environment. When the surface was melted by the laser, the preplaced powders dissolved, or partially dissolved into the melt and formed a phase or compound which enhanced the properties of the melt. If the powders partially dissolved, solid particles with a reduced size remained after the laser processing. These particles would also reinforce the surface and enhance the properties. The processed specimens were examined to characterise the microstructure, the hardness, the melt depth and the tendency to cracking. Since the thickness of the specimens has also an influence on the tendency to cracking, the effect of the specimen thickness in the nitriding plus powder alloying was also investigated. This is believed to be important in industrial applications where the thickness/size of the component to be treated must be considered.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

A continuous CO₂ 5kW laser was used at AEA Technology, Culham, UK. The beam had an annular shape and the energy was uniformly distributed in an annular area when the beam was in a stationary state. In the spinning beam mode the radius of the spinning locus (r_s) was set at 2 mm and the velocity of the spinning at 1500 rpm for all the experiments in the present work. Single tracks were melted. The laser power q was set at 2.8 kW, the specimen velocity v at 5, 10 or 15 mm.s⁻¹. A Ti-6Al-4V alloy (IMI 318) was used as the base alloy to be nitrided. The specimens were ground with 600 grit paper and cleaned with methanol before painting and then laser nitrided. Four types of particles, SiC(7 μ m), a mixture of SiC (7 μ m, 50v%) and Ti-6Al-4V (45 μ m, 50v%) powders, ZrC (45 μ m) and ZrN (45 μ m), were used as a preplaced layer and processed by a spinning laser beam under a gas contained 40%N and 60%Ar with a gas flow of 10 l.min⁻¹. These powders were blended with an organic solution and painted on the surface. During the processing, the specimens were moved under the laser on a work table with the surfaces to be treated at a defocused distance (DFD) of 15 mm above the focal point. Three levels of the specimen thickness (4, 10 and 18 mm) were used, and the dimensions of the surface were 100 mm \times 100 mm.

The microstructure, the melt pool depth and the profile of the transverse section were examined on an optical microscope. The hardness of the surface was measured on the transverse section of the specimens using a Mitutoyo MVK-G1 microhardness tester with a load of 100g, and given as a function of the depth below the surface. Wear resistance of these processed specimens were determined using a pin-on disc device using a constant load of 4.9 N and a speed of 0.236 ms⁻¹. The wear specimens were cleaned in methanol and blown dry with air before testing against P600 SiC grit paper, which was replaced every 25 m during each test. Weight losses were measured after a known sliding distance by weighing the sample to an accuracy of 10⁻⁵g. All tests were carried out at room temperature in air under dry sliding conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure

The microstructure developed in the specimen preplaced with SiC powder followed by laser nitriding, is shown Fig.1. No solid SiC particles remained after the laser nitriding. This showed a good agreement with our previous work [8] that only the SiC particles greater than $50\mu\text{m}$ had a chance to remain in the solid state after the preplaced SiC surface was laser processed under an argon environment. Fine dendrites formed in the melt pool. The phases developed under argon were identified as TiC and Ti_5Si_3 [9]. The phases formed in the melt shown in Fig.1 could be different from these, or more complex compounds containing a certain content of nitrogen since a nitrogen environment was used in the present work.

Fig.1 The microstructure developed in the 4 mm thick specimen preplaced with SiC powder and laser treated at 2.8 kW , 10 mms^{-1} .

The microstructure developed in the specimen preplaced with a mixture of SiC and Ti-6Al-4V alloy powders after laser nitriding shows similar features to those in Fig.1, except for a lower concentration of the dendrites formed in the melt pool. This is because less SiC was added into the melt shown in Fig.2 compared with that in Fig.1. A significant high concentration of nitrides formed in the top region of the melt in Fig.2, but the nitrides did not grow into a dendritic structure which was observed in a normal laser nitriding process [9]. It is considered that when SiC powder was preplaced on the surface, the preplaced layer separated the base alloy liquid from the nitrogen environment for a considerable time with respect to the liquid life-time, and therefore restricted the diffusion of nitrogen into the alloy melt pool. This resulted in fewer titanium nitrides forming in the melt shown in Fig.1 than that in Fig.2. In the case of the preplaced mixture of SiC and Ti64 powders, the Ti64 particles melted and were nitrided, but the nitrogen concentration in the melt was less than that in the melt developed on the surface without a preplaced layer. An insufficient concentration together with a high content of silicon and carbon in the liquid, resulted in a non-dendritic nitride layer formed in the top region of the melt.

Fig.3 shows the microstructure developed in the surface preplaced with ZrC powders. Large particles of ZrC (5-8 in the transverse section of the melt pool) remained after laser nitriding. The mean size of the particles of ZrC preplaced on the surface is 45 μ m. The size of the ZrC particle shown in Fig.3 is about 55 μ m, and no smaller ZrC particles were observed in the melt after the laser nitriding. This is in good agreement with our previous work [8] and indicates that a large size is required for the preplaced particle to remain undissolved after nitriding. The size required for the particle to remain undissolved also depends on the processing conditions. This can be seen clearly by comparing Fig.4 with Fig.5.

Fig.2 The microstructure developed in the 4 mm thick specimen preplaced with a mixture of SiC and Ti64 powders and laser treated at 2.8 kW, 5 mms⁻¹.

Fig.3 The microstructure developed in the 4 mm thick specimen preplaced with ZrC powder and laser treated at 2.8 kW, 5 mms⁻¹.

Both Figs.4 and 5 show the microstructures developed in the ZrN preplaced specimens but laser processed under different conditions. When a low specimen velocity was used, which gave a high laser energy density, no particles of ZrN remained in the melt, as shown in Fig.4. With a higher specimen velocity, the extent of the dissolution of these ZrN particles decreased, and some of the ZrN particles remained, but at a reduced size. This is shown in

Fig.5. Also it is seen in Fig.5 that the titanium nitrides near to the undissolved ZrN particles grew radially. This suggests that a nitrogen concentration gradient developed locally around the undissolved ZrN particles. A significant difference shown in Figs.4 and 5 from the previous figures is that a high concentration of titanium nitrides formed in the melts developed in the surfaces preplaced with ZrN particles. This must be attributed to a higher nitrogen concentration in the melt due to the dissolution of the ZrN particles. Typical titanium nitrides were observed in these two specimens as a thin continuous TiN (or more possibly $\text{TiN}_{0.8}$ [9]) layer formed at the top of the melt, and dendritic TiN grew from the continuous layer in a nearly perpendicular direction to the surface. It is interesting to note that at the top left corner of Fig.4, two continuous TiN layers formed in the melt which are likely to be branches from the original one. This is because the liquid melted in other areas was moved by the convective flow and filled the previously nitrated surface, due to the effect of overlapping of a spinning laser trace on the surface. Different sizes of $\text{TiN}_{0.3}$ needles (N) below the region of TiN (T) can be clearly seen in Figs.4 and 5.

Fig 4 The microstructure developed in the 4 mm thick specimen preplaced with ZrN powder and laser treated at 2.8 kW, 5 mm s^{-1} .

Fig 5 The microstructure developed in the 4 mm thick specimen preplaced with ZrN powder and laser treated at 2.8 kW, 10 mm s^{-1} .

Cracking Tendency

No cracking was observed in the 4 mm thick specimens, but cracks did occur in all the 17 mm thick specimens. This indicates that the thickness of the specimen has a significant influence

on the tendency to cracking. When the same laser processing conditions were used, a thicker specimen absorbed a smaller energy per unit volume and resulted in a higher cooling rate during the solidification of the melt. The effect of the thickness of the specimen on the cracking in the present work is in good agreement with our previous work on laser gas nitriding of Ti64 alloy [10], where a thick specimen (18 mm) was observed to have a high tendency to cracking.

The cracking tendency in the specimens preplaced with different types of powders can be seen from the 10 mm thick specimens. No cracking was observed except in the ZrN preplaced specimens. This is shown in Fig.6. Obviously, the high cracking tendency in the ZrN preplaced specimens could be related to the high concentration of titanium nitrides formed in the melt. In other words, no matter whether the nitrogen content is introduced into the melt by gas nitriding or by preplacement of the powders containing nitrogen, a high concentration of nitrides formed in the melt resulted in a high tendency to cracking. Therefore, one or both of the followings reduced the tendency to cracking in the specimens preplaced with other powders. Firstly, the compounds formed in the specimens preplaced with non-N-containing powders are less brittle, and secondly the compounds have a lower melting point than the titanium nitrides, and reduced the temperature range over which the development of residual stresses during the solidification of the melt occurred. However, a further analysis of the phases formed in the melts is required before this conclusion can be verified.

Fig.6 The microstructure developed in the 10 mm thick specimen preplaced with ZrN powder and laser treated at 2.8 kW, 10 mm^s⁻¹.

Melt Pool

There was no significant difference between the melt depths developed in the specimens preplaced with different powders. This is true even in the specimen preplaced with ZrN powder, in which a high concentration of titanium nitrides formed in the melt is considered to release a larger amount of heat than in the other specimens and therefore to develop a deeper melt. This may be explained by the fact that the heat of formation of the ZrN is -82.2 kcal/gmol, and that of TiN -73 kcal/gmol [11], and therefore the amount of heat released from the formation of TiN was only just sufficient to compensate that spent on the dissolution of ZrN when the same content of nitrogen in the preplaced powder is assumed.

Both the laser processing conditions and the thickness of the specimen have an influence on the melt depth. This is shown in Fig.7 for the SiC preplaced specimens of thickness 4, 10 and 17 mm at speeds 5, 10 and 15 mms^{-1} . The deepest position in the centre of the melt pool was measured for Fig.7. It can be seen that the thicker the specimen, the shallower the melt when the specimen speed is constant, and that the lower the speed, the deeper the melt pool for a given specimen. The relation between the specimen speed and the melt depth is linear. The influence of the specimen thickness is less significant when the thickness is greater than 10 mm. This is because when the specimen thickness is above a certain value, the specimen can be considered as a semi-infinite plate with respect to the heat flow developed by the laser beam. Therefore, melt pools developed in a semi-infinite plate under the same laser processing conditions are of constant depth.

Fig.7 The relations between the melt depth, the specimen speed and thickness.

Fig.8 A uniformly thick smooth surface MMC layer produced in the 4 mm thick specimen preplaced with a mixture of SiC and Ti64 powders and laser treated at 2.8 kW, 5 mms^{-1} .

The profile of the melt pool can be controlled by laser processing conditions. Under specific processing conditions, a uniformly thick smooth surface MMC was produced. Fig.8 shows a melt pool developed on the specimen preplaced with a mixture of SiC and Ti64 powders. It was reported in our previous work [12] that the melt pool profile was affected not only by the laser processing conditions, but also by the laser modes (the shape and the energy distribution

of the beam), and that a spinning beam was the only mode possible to produce a uniformly deep melt layer in comparison with a stationary Gaussian or annular beam. Fig.8 shows a good agreement with our previous work.

Microhardness

Fig.9 shows a group of the hardness profiles measured in the melt pools developed in the 5 mm thick specimens, which were given as a function of the depth below the surface. The SiC preplaced specimen has a hardness of 1200 HV at the top of the surface and then the hardness decreases sharply with the depth below the surface until a value of 600HV was achieved at depth of 200 μm. The hardness continues to decrease with melt depth but at a relative low rate until a nearly constant value 450-500 HV at the bottom of the melt. Both the hardness in the SiC+Ti64 preplaced specimen and that in the ZrN preplaced specimen reached a value over 700 HV. The ZrC preplaced specimen shows the lowest hardness. This is due to the fact that some large ZrC particles remained in the specimen and the hardness was measured only in the matrix with a micro-hardness tester. In other words, if a hardness tester with a 10 kg load had been used for the measurement of the same bulk material, the hardness in the melt of the ZrC preplaced specimen might have shown a higher hardness than that shown in Fig.9.

Fig.9 The hardness profiles of the surface layers developed in the 4 mm thick specimens.

Abrasive Wear Testing Results

The abrasive wear testing results are shown in Fig.10. A typical wear testing graph of the processed specimens consists of two periods of wearing: the wear in the surface layer and that in the base alloy after the surface layer was worn away. The wear graph of the base alloy is also presented in Fig.10 for comparison. All the laser processed specimens show a significant improvement in wear resistance in the surface layer, compared with that of the base alloy. As soon as the surface layer was worn away, the processed specimens had the same wear rate as that of the base alloy. A close relation between the hardness and the wear resistance can be clearly seen by comparing Fig.9 with Fig.10, i.e. the higher the hardness of the melt, the better the wear resistance. The specimen preplaced with SiC powder has the highest wear resistance. Therefore, to obtain a high wear resistant surface, a high hardness in a deep surface layer is

required with the harder phase being strongly bonded to the matrix. The undissolved ZrC and ZrN particles may have been detached and accelerated the wear rate by a three body wear mechanism.

Fig.10 The wear testing results for the base alloy and the 4 mm thick processed specimens.

CONCLUSIONS

1. A process of combining CO₂ laser powder alloying and nitriding was investigated in the present work to produce a crack-free high wear resistant surface of Ti64 alloy. Four types of powders (SiC, SiC+Ti64, ZrC and ZrN) were chosen in this investigation.
2. The surface preplaced with ZrN powder after laser nitriding has a higher tendency to cracking than the surfaces preplaced with other three powders. This is because the nitrogen content in the ZrN powder increased the volume of the titanium nitrides formed in the melt which is a cause of the cracking.
3. The thickness of the specimen has a significant influence on the tendency to cracking. The thicker the specimen, the greater the tendency to cracking when all the other conditions are constant.
4. The specimen preplaced with SiC powder achieved the highest hardness (1200 HV) of the four specimens. This suggests that the surface hardness can be controlled by the quantity of the SiC powder in a mixture of powders of SiC and the base alloy.
5. The abrasive wear testing showed that the higher the hardness of the surface, the higher the wear resistance, when the hard phase was well bonded to the matrix.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors of this paper gratefully acknowledge a financial support from EPSRC, UK and an ORS grant for Mr H. Xin. Thanks are due to Dr J. Fieret and Mr R. Heath for their assistance with the operation of the laser.

REFERENCES

1. Walker, A., Folkes, J., Steen, W.M. and West, D.R.F., "Laser Surface Alloying of Titanium Substrates with Carbon and Nitrogen", *J. Surf. Eng.*, vol. 1, 1985, pp. 23-29.
2. Morton, P.H., Bell, T., Weisheit, A., Kroll, J., Mordike, B.L. and Sagoo, K., "Laser Gas Nitriding of Titanium and Titanium Alloys", *Surface Modification Technologies 5*, Sudarshan, T. S. and Braza, J. F., The Institute of Materials, 1992, pp. 593-609.
3. Mridha, S. and Baker, T.N., "Crack Free Hard Surface Produced by Laser Nitriding of Commercial Purity Titanium", *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, vol. A188, 1994, pp. 229-239.
4. Kloosterman, A.B. and Hosson, J.Th.M. De., "Microstructural Characterization of Laser Nitrided Titanium", *Scripta Metallurgica et Materialia*, vol. 33, 1995, pp. 567-573.
5. Hu, C., Mridha, S., Ubhi, H.S., Bowen, A.W. and Baker, T.N., "Hardness, Dendrite Population and Microstructure under Different Environments in the Laser Nitrided Ti-6Al-4V Alloy", *Titanium '95: Science and the Technology*, Blenkinsop, P.A., Evans, W.J., and Flower, H.M., The Institute of Materials, London, UK, vol. 3, 1996, pp. 2835-2842.
6. Bell, T., Bergmann, H.W., Lanagan, J., Morton, P.H. and Staines, A.M., "Surface Engineering of Titanium with Nitrogen", *J. Surf. Eng.* vol. 2, 1986, pp. 133-143.
7. Mridha, S. and Baker, T.N., "Surface Cracking in Laser-Nitrided Titanium of Commercial Purity and Possible ways of Reducing These Defects", *Proc. Ad. Mater.*, vol. 4, 1994, pp. 85-94.
8. Mridha, S., Hu, C., Ubhi, H.S., Holdway, P., Bowen, A.W. and Baker, T.N., "Characteristic Features of the MMC Layer Formed on Ti-6Al-4V (IMI318) Alloy Surface through Laser Treatment by Using SiC Powder Injection and Preplacement Techniques", *Titanium '95: Science and the Technology*, Blenkinsop, P.A., Evans, W.J. and Flower, H.M., The Institute of Materials, London, UK, Vol. 3, 1996, pp. 1959-1966.
9. Hu, C., Xin, H., Watson, L. M. and Baker, T.N., "Analysis of the Phases Developed in Laser Nitriding Ti64 Alloys", *Acta. Metall. Mater.*, submitted for publication.
10. Hu, C. and Baker, T. N., "Overlapping Laser Tracks to Produce a Continuous Nitrided Layer in Ti-6Al-4V Alloy", *J. Mater. Sci.*, submitted for publication.
11. R.C. Weast and M.J. Astle (eds), *Handbook of Chemistry and Physics (61th edition)*, CRC Press, Florida, USA, 1980.
12. Hu, C. and Baker, T.N., "Influence of the Beam Mode in Laser Processing to Create a Surface Ti-SiC_p MMC", *Proceedings of 5th International Conference on Improvement of Materials*, Liu, J., MATEC, Paris-Marne La Vallee, 1996, pp. 167-176.